

MERCURATION OF ACETYLURETHANE AND ITS SUBSTITUTED AMIDES.

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The preparation and properties of the mercury derivatives of acetylurethane and its substituted amides have been described by following the method of Naik and Shah.

In view of the molecular structure of acetylurethane $\text{Me}\cdot\text{CONH}\cdot\text{COOEt}$, the hydrogen attached to the nitrogen atom may be expected to be replaceable by metals. The present paper deals with the preparation and properties of the mercury derivatives of acetylurethane and its substituted amides obtained by the action of mercury acetamide in aqueous or alcoholic solution. The following substances have been investigated.

(1) Acetylurethane, (2) acetylphenylcarbamide, (3) acetyl-*m*-tolylcarbamide, (4) acetyl-*o*-tolylcarbamide, (5) acetyl-*p*-tolylcarbamide, (6) acetyl- α -naphthylcarbamide, (7) acetyl β -naphthylcarbamide, (8) acetyl 1:3:4-xyllyl carbamide, (9) acetyl-*p*-anisylcarbamide, (10) phenylurethane. All give compounds of the general formula $(\text{Me}\cdot\text{CONCOR})_2\text{Hg}$ where R may be a phenyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-tolyl, naphthyl or xyllyl group. In the case of compound (10) mercury bis-phenylurethane was obtained. The method used for the mercuration of these amides is the one used for the first time by Naik and Shah (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 29).

The compounds are decomposed by dilute hydrochloric acid and by hydrogen, ammonium or sodium sulphides, the corresponding mercury salt being formed. With potassium iodide the following reaction occurs:—

Phenylhydrazine and hydrazine hydrate liberate metallic mercury.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Mercury bis-acetylurethane was precipitated when an aqueous solution of mercury acetamide and acetylurethane were mixed. It crystallises from hot water in colourless needles, m. p. 174°. (Found: N, 6.46; Hg, 43.72. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6\text{N}_2\text{Hg}$ requires N, 6.09; Hg, 43.48 per cent).

Potassium iodide liberates 1.87 equivalents of alkali as against 2 equivalents required. Ether extracts acetylurethane from the solution obtained

with 0.25 N-HCl. With phenylhydrazine mercury is at once liberated with evolution of nitrogen.

Mercury bis-acetylphenylcarbamide was precipitated when mercury acetamide and acetylphenylcarbmide were heated under reflux in methyl alcohol, m.p. 205-206° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.01; Hg, 35.88. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4N_4Hg$ requires N, 10.11; Hg, 36.1 per cent).

Acetyl-m-tolylcarbamide was formed by heating acetylurethane and m-toluidine in equimolecular proportions for 30 minutes at 160°. The solid separating on addition of water was dissolved in hot acetic acid and cooled. Di-m-tolylurea, which separated on cooling, was removed and the filtrate diluted with water to precipitate the required amide which was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 128°. (Found: N, 14.37. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 14.58 per cent).

With mercury acetamide in methyl alcoholic solution, it forms *mercury acetyl-m-tolylcarbamide*, m.p. 196-97°. (Found: N, 10.05; Hg, 34.79. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4N_4Hg$ requires N, 9.65; Hg, 34.36 per cent).

Mercury bis-acetyl-o-tolylcarbamide was similarly prepared, m.p. 209-10°. (Found: N, 9.58; Hg, 34.04. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4N_4Hg$ requires N, 9.65; Hg, 34.36 per cent). Treatment with potassium iodide and hydrochloric acid reforms the amide.

Mercury bis-acetyl p-tolylcarbamide has m.p. 227-28° (with rapid decomposition). (Found: N, 9.78; Hg, 34.22. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4N_4Hg$ requires N, 9.65; Hg, 34.36 per cent).

Mercury bis-acetyl-a-naphthylcarbamide has m.p. 225-28° (decomp.). (Found: N, 8.31; Hg, 30.11. $C_{26}H_{22}O_4N_4Hg$ requires N, 8.56; Hg, 30.58 per cent).

Mercury bis-acetyl-β-naphthylcarbamide has m.p. 215-16° (decomp.), (Found: N, 8.79; Hg, 29.44. $C_{26}H_{22}O_4N_4Hg$ requires N, 8.56; Hg, 30.58 per cent).

Acetyl-1:3:4-xyllylcarbamide was extracted by ethyl acetate from the product formed by heating equimolecular proportions of acetylurethane and 1:3:4-xylidine at 160° per 1 hour and pouring into water. This is identical with the compound prepared from 1:3:4-xyllylcarbamide and acetyl chloride in pyridine solution.

Mercury bis-acetyl-1:3:4-xyllylcarbamide has m.p. 231-32° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.15; Hg, 33.12. $C_{22}H_{26}O_4N_4Hg$ requires N, 9.18; Hg, 32.79 per cent).

Acetyl p-anisylcarbamide was formed by heating acetylurethane and *p*-anisidine in equimolecular proportions at 160° for 2 hours. It separates dilute acetic acid in needles, m. p. $172-73^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 13.38. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.46 per cent).

Mercury bis-acetyl-p-anisylcarbamide has m. p. 222° (decomp.). (Found: N, 8.87; Hg, 32.93. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4N_4Hg$ requires N, 9.12; Hg, 32.57 per cent).

Mercury bis-phenylurethane was precipitated by adding water to the solution obtained by heating mercury acetamide and phenylurethane in methyl alcohol for 30 minutes, m. p. 203° . (Found: N, 5.45; Hg, 37.47. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4N_2Hg$ requires N, 5.30; Hg, 37.87 per cent).

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